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Multi-criteria assessment of energy systems at an office building

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Abstract

Over the past few decades, there has been a significant rise in energy consumption within the construction sector. Thus, the focus has now shifted on designing new buildings or retrofitting existing structures with reduced energy demands while ensuring optimal indoor thermal comfort conditions for building occupants. In the current study, a combined energy, techno-economic, environmental and thermal comfort assessment of a number of energy technologies and systems in an existing office building is presented. The energy analysis and modelling of the building are carried out using the DesignBuilder and JEPlus software. The assessment is carried out in terms of the calculation of four Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); the primary energy consumption (kWh/m²), the carbon dioxide emissions (kgCO₂), net present cost of the systems, and indoor thermal discomfort hours for approximately 200 design scenarios. The ultimate objective of this paper is to identify the benefits of each examined energy system on the specified KPIs and to determine the most suitable design strategy and optimal combination of these technologies using a multi-criteria assessment approach based on the PROMETHEE method.

1. Introduction

One of the most significant challenges for future buildings is enhancing the energy efficiency and environmental footprint throughout all phases of a building's lifecycle, from construction to demolition. Currently, building sector is responsible for 36% of global energy usage and consequently contributes to 39% of worldwide carbon dioxide emissions [1]. Thus, addressing energy conservation and the shift to eco-friendly technologies has become a paramount concern. The European Union (EU) has introduced regulations to improve energy efficiency, reduce energy consumption, and eliminate wastage through the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2010/31/EU) [2]. The latest recast of the EPBD mandates a long-term strategy to transform existing buildings into nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (nZEB) by 2050.

The use of passive and active efficient energy systems aims at saving energy, and reducing the environmental footprint of both existing and future buildings. Passive strategies, such as adding thermal insulation and replacing windows, can achieve even more than 40% energy savings [3]. Thermal insulation depends on its thickness and thermal properties, while the optimal combination varies based on the building's use and the climate conditions. Energy efficient windows, like triple pane low-e, contribute to reduction of thermal losses and at the same time the low-e glazing minimizes the infrared and ultraviolet radiation without reducing visible light. Moreover, innovative smart glazing like electrochromic windows that change their optical properties regarding transparency and absorption of solar radiation, modulate daylight and solar energy entering indoor spaces [4].

Combining the above passive systems with active strategies, such as HVAC improvements, can further increase energy savings by up to 80% [3]. Installing photovoltaic systems (PVs), using advanced building management system to control the indoor conditions of each space in the building, and opting for eco-friendly fuels like natural gas or biomass for the heating systems can potentially result in an nZEB.

Besides energy and environmental performance, the economic aspects of the aforementioned passive and active energy systems, as well as maintaining high levels of indoor thermal comfort, should be considered during the building's design phase. Often, an energy-efficient system may not be eco-friendly, or if it has a low

environmental footprint, it might be costly or fail to provide adequate thermal comfort for the building's residents. Thus, multiple factors must be considered to assess a building's overall effectiveness and functionality. To manage this complex task, a multi-criteria decision-making process is necessary.

In the current study, 216 parameterized cases for an office building, combining different passive and active systems, are assessed in terms of energy performance, environmental footprint, economic and thermal comfort aspects, by use of appropriate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). All cases are thoroughly simulated using DesignBuilder software, and the parameterized study is conducted using JEPlus software. The selected KPIs are the primary energy consumption, the equivalent of carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂), the Net Present Cost (NPC) of the installation and operation of the systems for a lifetime of 25 years, and finally the thermal discomfort hours within the building. Last but not least, the assessment results are evaluated through multi-criteria analysis. The ultimate goal of the work is to select the optimal scenario by evaluating the aforementioned KPIs using the PROMETHEE multi-criteria analysis method.

2. Methodology

2.1 Description of the building model

The current study examines an office building located in Athens at the campus of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). It is a north oriented ground floor building, with a total floor area of 65m², divided into three spaces (thermal zones). The north-oriented thermal zone covers 32.5 m², while there are two south-oriented thermal zones, covering 16.3 m² each, as depicted in Figure 1. The building, constructed in 2021, is a prefabricated composite construction based on “Cargotecture” (steel load bearing frame from shipping containers with detachable and alternating structural elements) and drywall systems. There are four windows, two facing north with dimensions of 1.37m × 1.37m, and two glass doors facing south with dimensions of 1.37m × 2.05m. The total Window to Wall Ratio (WWR) is approximately 8.7%. The external walls are constructed with gypsum board, OSB panels, steel of shipping container and cement board insulated with materials polyurethane and EPS. The roof is constructed with corrugated structural steel deck, a roofing membrane, EPS, polyurethane, OSB and gypsum board and the ground floor is constructed with concrete slab, EPS, polyurethane and floor tiles.

Figure 1 View of the examined building a) real and b) in DesignBuilder software

2.2 Parametrized cases

In this paper, in total 216 different cases of passive and active systems are being examined. More specifically, three different thermal insulation thicknesses of EPS at external walls, roof and floor are considered, 5 cm, 10 cm, and 15 cm respectively. Concerning the transparent elements, two types of windows are examined, a simple triple low-e and a triple electrochromic. The triple low-e windows use internal shading, while the triple electrochromic ones use a Daylight Illuminance protocol based on which the state of the electrochromic pane adjusts to achieve a luminance level of 500 lux according to the assumptions in the building space.

Regarding the active systems, two basic heating systems are being studied. The first heating system comprises a boiler paired with fan coils as terminal units, while the second heating system integrates a boiler with floor heating as its terminal unit. Two alternative boilers are considered: the first one is a condensing gas boiler with an efficiency of 95% and the second one utilizes biomass with an efficiency of 78%. Furthermore,

the above heating systems are combined with three scenarios of thermostat temperatures: 20°C, 21°C, and 22°C. Last but not least, the presence of photovoltaic systems (PVs) is also examined, investigating three cases, one without PVs, and two cases with a total surface area of 10m² and 20m², respectively. Table 1 summarizes the parameterized scenarios.

Table 1 Parametrized cases

	Parametrized cases		
Insulation Thickness	5cm	10cm	15cm
Windows	Triple low-e		Triple electrochromic
HVAC Terminal Units	Fancoils		Floor heating
Boilers	Natural Gas		Biomass
Thermostat	20°C	21°C	22°C
Photovoltaic Systems	0 m ²	10 m ²	20 m ²

For all cases, the cooling system is a combination of a heat pump with fan coils as terminal units. The Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the heat pump is assumed equal to 3, while the cooling setpoint is set to 26°C. Further assumptions of the building model, such as the internal loads from lighting (8.3 W/m²), electric equipment (8.3 W/m²) and people's presence (0.054 person/m²), infiltration (0.3 ac/h) and natural ventilation (0.00046 m³/s/m²), are based on ASHRAE [5] values and schedules for an office building.

Based on the aforementioned examined cases of the EPS insulation thickness, the U-values of the building envelope surfaces are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Thermal Transmittance of the building envelope surfaces

U-value of building's surfaces [W/m ² K]			
Insulation Thickness	0.05m	0.1m	0.15m
External Wall	0.49	0.29	0.21
Roof	0.43	0.27	0.19
Groundfloor	0.50	0.29	0.21

Regarding the thermal properties of the building's transparent elements, the triple low-e windows have a u-value of 0.69 W/m²K, a g-value of 0.41, and a visible transmittance (VT) of 0.54. The triple electrochromic windows have u-value of 0.71 W/m²K, g-value of 0.32-0.10 and VT of 0.55-0.14. The two g-values and VT values represent the clear and dark states of the electrochromic windows respectively.

2.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

2.3.1 Energy Performance

One of the crucial KPIs for evaluating the energy efficiency of building scenarios is the primary energy consumption per unit of floor area [6]. This metric represents the energy that has not undergone any conversion or transformation processes. This indicator holds significant importance within the EPBD [2] and pertains to the total annual energy consumption for heating and cooling purposes. The primary energy per unit floor area is evaluated by the following equation:

$$PE = \frac{\sum_i E_{d,i} \cdot PEF_i - E_{p,i} \cdot PEF_{el}}{A} \quad 1$$

where, PE is the primary energy consumption, A the floor area, E_d is the delivered energy required to meet the energy demands of considered end-uses of the building for heating and cooling from each fuel source *i*, PEF_{*i*} is the primary energy factor that converts the energy use of fuel *i* to primary, E_{p,*i*} is the produced energy on site from active systems such as photovoltaics and PEF_{el} is the primary energy factor that converts the energy use from electricity to primary. In Greece the primary energy factor for natural gas is 1.05, for biomass is 1 and for electricity is 2.5 [7].

2.3.2 Environmental Assessment

Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions result from the operation of energy systems used for heating and cooling. These emissions are typically calculated annually in units of mass, such as kilograms (kg) CO₂ or CO₂ equivalents. This conversion is achieved using the energy consumption and predetermined conversion emission factors. The mass of CO₂ emissions per year is defined by the following equation:

$$GHG = \frac{TE_H \cdot GEF_H + TE_C \cdot GEF_C - TE_p \cdot GEF_{el}}{A} \quad 2$$

Where TE_H and TE_C are the heating and cooling consumption of the energy systems per year [kWh/year], respectively, while GEF_H and GEF_C are the predetermined conversion factors of greenhouse gas emission for the weighted average based on energy consumption source/fuel mix [kgCO_{2eq}/kWh]. TE_p is the produced energy on site from active systems and GEF_{el} is the greenhouse gas emission factor for electricity. In Greece the factor of CO₂ emissions (kg/kWh) is 0.196 for natural gas and 0.989 for electricity [7]. Regarding the use of biomass as fuel, the greenhouse gas emission factor is zero, so the carbon footprint is zero. The environmental friendliness of biomass arises from the fact that its production involves natural raw materials such as logging residues, sawdust, special crops, which absorb an equal amount of CO₂ during their growth as they emit during combustion, thus the overall carbon dioxide transfer balance to the atmosphere is zero [8].

2.3.3 Net Present Cost

In financial engineering, there are certain types of projects, like the case examined in this paper, in which, due to their inherent characteristics, there are no sales or revenues. In these cases, the Net Present Cost (NPC) parameter is commonly used. When evaluating two or more systems for the same time period, the system with the lowest NPC is the optimal one [9]. The NPC is calculated through the following equation:

$$NPC = \sum_{t=0}^N \frac{AA_{TC}}{(1+i)^t} + I_{CC} \quad 3$$

In NPC analysis, the annual total expenses or costs (AA_{TC}) are given as positive values and therefore, the NPC at the end of the system's lifespan will be positive. The annual total expenses involve the cost for heating, cooling and maintenance of the systems minus the profit from selling the produced energy from the photovoltaic systems. The i represents the discount rate and assumed equal to 6%, while the t is the lifetime period in which the NPC is evaluated, equal to 25 years. Lastly, the I_{CC} represents the initial investment cost for the installation of the systems, which is calculated by the distinct costs presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Cost of all building's systems

System	Cost	System	Cost	System	Cost
Natural Gas Boiler	1600€	Circulator Pump	150€	EPS 5cm	5€/m ²
Biomass Boiler	2100€	Pipes	2.7€/m ²	Insulation installation	30€/m ²
Heat Pump	4000€	PV installation	190€/m ²	Triple low-e	760€/m ²
Fan coil	300€	Maintenance	15-35€/year	Triple EC	1050€/m ²

2.3.4 Thermal Comfort

The indoor environment, encompassing factors such as temperature, humidity, and air velocity, has a profound impact not only on the energy usage of buildings but also on the health, productivity, and comfort of the occupants. ISO 7730 delineates thermal comfort as the state of mind reflecting contentment with the thermal surroundings. The Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) index employs heat balance principles to correlate six key factors influencing thermal comfort with the average response of individuals on the thermal sensation scale. According to ASHRAE standard 55 [10], the comfort zone is defined by the combination of major variables of indoor thermal environmental factors and personal factors, that produce acceptable conditions for the majority of the occupants within a space. These factors are metabolic rate, effective mechanical power, clothing insulation, air temperature, mean radiant temperature, relative air velocity and relative humidity. According to the technical standard EN 15251, discomfort time considers the sum of the discomfort hours with more than 10% dissatisfaction. Based on the above, there is a Thermal Discomfort index that evaluates the thermal comfort based on the equation:

$$TD = \frac{\sum_i \tau_i A_i}{A_t} \quad 4$$

where τ_i is the number of discomfort hours in an area A_i divided by the total floor area A_t .

2.4 Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) method - PROMETHEE

Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methods enable the construction of intricate hierarchical models [11], preference modelling [12], and the consideration of uncertainty and imprecision in both data and preferences [13]. These methods necessitate values representing the significance of evaluation criteria, which can either be subjectively determined by decision-makers or calculated using objective techniques. Among the advanced priority ranking methods, Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation (PROMETHEE) is a superior method for ranking and selecting from a limited set of alternatives [14]. Within the PROMETHEE family, which includes PROMETHEE I, PROMETHEE II, and various expansions, PROMETHEE II stands out for its simplicity and its capability to address conflicting criteria giving a complete ranking for all the alternative examined cases. Particularly in preference selection, the preference structure of PROMETHEE is based on pairwise comparisons. To implement PROMETHEE II effectively, two pieces of information are necessary, the criterion weights and preference functions [15].

The first stage of the method is to normalize the decision matrix of the KPIs (x_{ij}) for each selected KPI (i) and each alternative case. In the examined cases, all the KPIs are considered as non-beneficial criteria, as the best solution involves the smallest value of each indicator. Non-beneficial criteria are calculated through the equation 5.

$$R_{ij} = \frac{\max(x_{ij}) - x_{ij}}{\max(x_{ij}) - \min(x_{ij})} \quad 5$$

After calculating the evaluative differences of each alternative with respect to other alternatives $x_{ik} - x_{jk}$, the preference function is defined by the following function.

$$p_k(x_i, x_j) = \begin{cases} 0, & x_{ik} < x_{jk} \\ H_k(x_{ik} - x_{jk}), & x_{ik} \geq x_{jk} \end{cases} \quad 6$$

The next step is to calculate the aggregated preference indices and outranking flows. The aggregated preference function is defined as:

$$\pi(x_i, x_j) = \sum_{k=1}^n w_k p_k(x_i, x_j) \pi(x_j, x_i) = \sum_{k=1}^n w_k p_k(x_j, x_i) \quad 7$$

Where $\pi(x_i, x_j)$ is expressing with which degree x_i is preferred to x_j over the KPIs and $\pi(x_j, x_i)$ how is x_j preferred to x_i . Afterwards, the leaving (positive) and the entering (negative) outranking flows are determined. Each alternative scenario x_i is facing (n-1) other alternatives.

- The positive outranking flow:

$$\varphi^+(x_i) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \pi(x_i, x_j) \quad 8$$

- The negative outranking flow:

$$\varphi^-(x_i) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \pi(x_j, x_i) \quad 9$$

The positive flows express how the alternative scenario x_i is outranking all the others. Higher the $\varphi^+(x_i)$, refers to better alternative. On the other side, the negative outranking expresses how an alternative scenario is outranked by all the other. The lower the $\varphi^-(x_i)$, is, the better the alternative. Finally, requesting a complete ranking, the net outranking flow can be considered:

$$\varphi(x_i) = \varphi^+(x_i) - \varphi^-(x_i) \quad 10$$

As the decision-maker requests complete ranking, in the balance between the positive and the negative outranking flows, the higher the net flow, the better the alternative.

3. Results

3.1 Energy Performance

Figure 2 depicts the primary energy consumption for heating, cooling, and lighting in relation to increasing insulation thickness, considering two types of windows and two different terminal unit systems. The fixed

parameters are the boiler, being the one using natural gas, the thermostat temperature set to 20°C and the PVs that are non-existent. As shown, the fan coil systems consume 7%-16% less primary energy compared to floor heating systems, because the floor heating requires a larger volume of water, which in turn requires more energy to heat. As insulation thickness increases, the building's energy demand for heating decreases. Specifically, heating demands decrease by 10% when insulation increases from 0.05m to 0.1m, and by 5% when it increases from 0.1m to 0.15m. Conversely, cooling demands increase by approximately 1.5% for every 5cm increase in insulation thickness. Despite this, the overall primary energy consumption declines because the reduction in heating demands is more significant. Additionally, installing electrochromic triple windows instead of triple low-e windows results in a 1.3%-2.5% reduction in primary energy consumption when the terminal units of the heating system are fan coils, and a 0.6%-1.8% reduction when floor heating is installed. The greatest decrease in both scenarios occurs with an insulation thickness of 0.15m. Although both window types have similar U-values, triple low-e windows have a higher g-value. A higher g-value means greater solar gains, thus reducing heating energy requirements while increasing cooling demands. The conversion factor to primary energy is 2.5 for electricity and 1.05 for natural gas, making the decrease in cooling demands more impactful in the overall primary energy calculation. Finally, the installation of the electrochromic windows reduces lighting consumption by about 3%, thus resulting in the overall decrease of primary energy consumption in this case. This reduction is due to the shading properties of triple low-e windows, which have internal shading. Because of the internal shading, the artificial lighting is necessary in order to maintain the brightness level at 500 lux, which are essential for an office building. In contrast, electrochromic windows use the "Meet daylight illuminance" protocol, adjusting to maintain a desired brightness level of 500 lux.

Figure 2 Primary energy as a function of insulation thickness

Figure 3 illustrates the primary energy consumption for heating, cooling, and lighting as a function of three thermostat temperatures, considering two types of windows and two different heating systems. As shown, increasing the thermostat by 1°C, the primary energy consumption is increased by 5%-6% due to the increased heating demands, for both the fan coil system and the floor heating system.

Figure 3 Primary energy as a function of thermostat temperature

3.2 Environmental Footprint

Figure 4 illustrates the CO₂ emissions depending on the presence of PVs and the combination of heating systems (natural gas or biomass boiler and fan coil or floor heating for terminal unit). Overall, the building's CO₂ emissions are significantly reduced if a PV system of 10m² is installed, since the emissions are mainly influenced by the cooling system, using electricity with a conversion factor of 0.989. Regarding the heating systems, the CO₂ emissions are approximately 100-170 kgCO₂/year with a natural gas boiler, since the conversion factor is just 0.196. In contrast, with a biomass boiler, CO₂ emissions are zero due to the CO₂ emission conversion factor for biomass being zero, according to the Hellenic Directive (KENAK). Lastly, the building's environmental impact is improved when the terminal units are the fan coils, due to the primary energy consumption reduction.

Figure 4 CO₂ emissions as a function of PV area

3.3 Net Present Cost

Figure 5 displays the Net Present Cost (NPC) over a 25-year lifetime as a function of PVs area for each terminal unit. The NPC accounts for energy consumption, system maintenance costs over the building's lifespan, and the initial investment required for installing the building's systems. The initial cost is significantly higher than the operational cost due to the excellent efficiency of the active systems and constitutes the largest proportion of the NPC.

In comparison, the NPC for the floor heating is 11% higher than that of the fan coil system. This disparity arises from both the higher annual energy consumption and the greater initial investment cost associated with the floor heating system. Furthermore, an increase of 1% in NPC is observed for every 10m² increase in PV area. Despite that the operational cost is significantly reduced by 35%-54% for each additional 10m² of PV area, the NPC is increased by 1% due to the increase of initial investment (7%).

Figure 5 Net Present Cost as a function of Photovoltaic (PV) area

Figure 6 Net Present Cost as a function of insulation thickness

Figure 6 illustrates the Net Present Cost (NPC) as a function of insulation thickness for each heating system. As shown, the NPC is lower for the fan coil system compared to the floor heating system, consistent with the

findings in Figure 5. When the insulation thickness increases from 0.05m to 0.1m, the NPC decreases by 1% for the fan coil system and by 3% for the floor heating system. Conversely, when the insulation thickness increases from 0.1m to 0.15m, the NPC increases by 2% for the fan coil system and by 1% for the floor heating system. Therefore, although the initial cost of installing 0.1m of insulation instead of 0.05m is 5% higher, the NPC is reduced, due to the significant lower operational cost by 0.7% - 3%. The above analysis is based on a thermostat setting of 20°C. However, the graph exhibits similar behaviour even when the temperature is set to 21°C or 22°C.

3.4 Thermal Comfort

It was observed that thermal discomfort hours occur during the heating period. Figure 7 shows the discomfort hours for whole year at three different thermostat temperatures for each window type and terminal unit. Overall, the floor heating system results in 22%-44% fewer discomfort hours compared to the fan coil system. This is because floor heating provides a uniform distribution of heat throughout the space, ensuring better comfort conditions. The fewest discomfort hours occur at a thermostat setting of 22°C. Additionally, using triple low-e windows instead of electrochromic triple windows reduces discomfort hours up to 9% (up to 200 hours) for both terminal units, depending on the thermostat temperature. This is attributed to the fact that electrochromic triple windows have a lower g-value, leading to reduced solar gains, which can cause a feeling of uncomfortable cold during the winter for the building's residents.

Figure 7 Discomfort hours as a function of thermostat temperature

3.5 Multi-Criteria Assessment

The previous results showed that there is no examined case that simultaneously has the lowest primary energy consumption, the least CO₂ emissions in kg, the lowest Net Present Cost (NPC) and the fewest hours of non-thermal comfort conditions. Therefore, the use of a multi-criteria analysis methodology was chosen, specifically the PROMETHEE method. The first step of the method is the selection of alternative solutions. As alternative solutions, 216 cases are introduced, meaning all the alternatives concerning 2 boilers, 2 terminal units, 3 insulation thickness alternatives and 2 types of glazing systems. Additionally, they concern the presence or absence of photovoltaics in the building and how many square meters they occupy, and finally, they concern the choice of the thermostat operating temperature. The second step is the selection of criteria. Four KPIs were chosen that examine in each case the primary energy consumption, CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere, the Net Present Cost, and Thermal Discomfort. The final step is to determine the weights for each criterion that was set. For the determination of the weights used in the multi-criteria method, four alternative scenarios were decided, which are presented in Table 4. For the determination of the weights in the 1st scenario a questionnaire was used, which contains questions for evaluating the criteria of all the interventions that were examined. The questionnaire was developed and completed within the framework of the European research project PLURAL (No 958218) [16]. The conclusions from the questionnaire indicate that the most important indicator is the economic viability of the systems (41.3%), followed by the primary energy consumption (22.7%). In the 2nd scenario, all KPIs were considered equally important, thus each having a weight of 25%. For the 3rd scenario, aiming to place greater emphasis on reducing the environmental footprint of the systems, the weight of this KPI was set at 40%. The remaining KPIs were considered equally important at 20% each. In the 4th scenario, the question raised was what the optimal solution would be if greater weight was given to the

thermal comfort experienced by the building occupants. With this goal, the weight of Thermal Comfort was set at 40%, while the other KPIs were given equal importance at 20% each.

Table 4 The weight factors for four alternative scenarios

Weights	Energy	CO2	NPC	Thermal Comfort
1st scenario	22.7%	18.7%	41.3%	17.4%
2st scenario	25%	25%	25%	25%
3st scenario	20%	40%	20%	20%
4st scenario	20%	20%	20%	40%

The results from the Multi-Criteria Assessment are presented in Table 5. The multi-criteria methodology application showed that the most economical and environmentally friendly terminal unit is fan coils, while the floor heating system provides greater thermal comfort. In each scenario the optimal solution for the thermostat temperature is 22°C, despite the Greek regulation that define the heating setpoint at 20°C [7], while regarding the windows, triple low-e glazing emerged as the optimal solution. For boiler type, the natural gas boiler was optimal when the economic criterion was prioritized due to its low purchase and operating costs, but the biomass boiler was the most environmentally friendly option. Lastly, in each scenario, 15 cm insulation thickness was found to be ideal, offering maximum energy savings with the lowest cost, lowest CO₂ emissions, and greatest thermal comfort for the building's occupants. Additionally, in each scenario, a photovoltaic system with a 20m² surface area emerged as the most economically advantageous solution.

Table 5 Multi-Criteria assessment Results

	1st Weight Scenario	2nd Weight Scenario	3rd Weight Scenario	4th Weight Scenario
Terminal Unit	Fan coil	Fan coil	Fan coil	Floor heating
Insulation Thickness	0.15 m	0.15 m	0.15 m	0.15 m
Glazing	Triple low-e	Triple low-e	Triple low-e	Triple low-e
PV area	20 m ²	20 m ²	20 m ²	20 m ²
Heating system's fuel	Natural Gas	Natural Gas	Biomass	Natural Gas
Thermostat temperature	22°C	22°C	22°C	22°C

4. Conclusion

In the present work, a combined energy, environmental, techno-economic and comfort evaluation of energy technologies and systems was conducted in an existing office building. Alternative cases were examined for the heating system, including the type of boiler based on its fuel and the terminal units, as well as the thickness of insulation, different types of glazing, the installation or not of photovoltaic systems, and the use of a thermostat for different temperature settings. A total of 216 cases were evaluated in terms of energy efficiency, environmental behaviour, economic viability, and thermal comfort conditions. For their evaluation, four KPIs were defined, primary energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, Net Present Cost (NPC), and hours of thermal discomfort. These indicators for all alternatives were calculated using the DesignBuilder and JEPlus software. The energy evaluation of the alternative cases showed that a heating system with fan coil terminals requires 7%-16% less energy compared to floor heating system. Additionally, energy savings are achieved by increasing the insulation thickness (up to 16%) or changing the glazing type from triple low-e to electrochromic triple (5% - 10%). Specifically, for glazing cases, it was found that the use of electrochromic windows increased the final consumption for heating but reduced the final consumption for cooling and lighting, making them preferable in terms of primary energy consumption. It was also noted that with 20m² of photovoltaics, the building becomes nearly zero energy. In the environmental assessment, zero CO₂ emissions for heating were observed when biomass was used as fuel, due to its zero-emission coefficient. The techno-economic evaluation of the alternatives through NPC calculation showed that floor heating is not the optimal choice, with

a total cost increase of 11% compared to the fan coil system. However, an interesting conclusion is the cost reduction in the case of 20m² of photovoltaic system's area. Although the initial investment is 7% higher for each additional 10m² of PV area, the annual energy consumption decreases significantly by 35%-54%. In terms of thermal comfort evaluation, the most notable conclusion is that the floor heating system offers greater thermal comfort to the building's occupants with 22%-44% less discomfort hours. Additionally, thermal discomfort hours are fewer when the thermostat is set to 22°C.

Finally, the above analysis led to the application of a multi-criteria methodology to identify the best alternative among the 216 cases. The Promethee method was chosen, using four different weighting scenarios. The approach, implemented in the current study, highlights the importance of a multi-criteria assessment during an early stage of building design or renovation, taking into consideration a multitude of criteria, such as energy performance, environmental impact, financial aspects and thermal comfort. The method can be further generalized in the future to take into account additional criteria and parameters, such as visual comfort or social aspects, while in respect of the decarbonization of the building stock, life cycle assessment of the alternative cases should be taken also into consideration.

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